

Seven prose poems by Hadaa Sendoo

I don't have any beautiful gifts, but before departing
I will leave a lovely poem of mine for you.

I am a lonely rock,
I have the gentle skin of water, the bright eyes of a fish.

Earth, I came bearing hope.
In the mortal world, I returned in disappointment.

The quiet murmur of breeze in the woods.
But I brought a lot of noise.

The year is drawing to a close, I've done nothing.
I woke up to watch the sunrise, and the sunset afterglow only.

I would be a bee gathering nectar from the garden.
It takes away the sweet and leaves behind the fragrance of the flowers.

I remember my childhood in a daze, I gazing at the vast night sky, counting the
countless stars on my fingers.
And my reckless youth was much like a Spanish bullfight.

11 aphorisms from "On Poetry"

Great poets are willing to be alone and treat every poem and every soul sincerely.

Where words cannot reach, may the imagery of poetry reach.

Although a poem carries the poet's emotions, it should not be an outlet for bad moods
that even the MUSES dislike.

In my time, I would rather compromise myself than compromise my poetry.

In this life, some beautiful places I can never reach, poetry will take me there.

Poetry is like ancient folk songs, making my anxiety and even resentment gentle and calm.

Poetry is my religion and I must kiss it devoutly.

One morning, I died, but poetry was alive. It was all of my dreams.

Poetry is written for the soul and the universe, the sky and the steppe, just as the sky is written for the snow-capped mountains and the white clouds.

The woman I was passionately in love with betrayed me, but that extremely loyal poem never abandoned me.

Let the last poem of my life be as enduring as Yanni's musical work "The Nightingale".

Bio:

Hadaa Sendoo, born in 1961, is a Mongolian poet, known for his modern poetry. He has published over 20 books of poetry, and his works have been translated into multiple languages. He founded the World Poetry Almanac in 2006, which showcases contemporary poetry from around the globe. Many of his poems depict the beauty and vastness of the Mongolian landscape. His contributions to literature have made him a significant figure in the 21st-century poetry landscape, and his works continue to resonate with readers around the world. Since 1991 he has lived in Ulaanbaatar, the capital of Mongolia.